

Studies in the Complexes of Anthrones with Metal Halides Part V. Metal Halide Complexes of 10-Methyleneanthrone

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Methyleneanthrone forms solid coloured complexes with chlorides of antimony (V), bismuth (III) and chlorides and bromides of boron and aluminium (III) in the ratio 1:1 and with tin, titanium and zirconium chlorides and bromides in the ratio 2:1. It does not form addition complexes with iodides of these metals. The complexes of tin (IV) and antimony (V) halides are nonionic and monomeric in nitrobenzene. Thermogravimetric analysis of titanium (IV) halide adducts suggests their existence as addition dimers. Unlike complexes of other metal halides, titanium (IV) halide adducts do not show lowering of carbonyl stretching frequency in the infrared spectra. The probable reason has been discussed.

The preparation of complexes of various metal halides with anthrone, benzanthrone, 10-nitroanthrone, 10-benzal-anthrone and 10,10-dibenzylanthrone and some physico-chemical investigations on the measurement of their molar conductance, molecular weight, infra-red spectrum, thermogravimetric analysis and magnetic susceptibility have already been reported by the authors¹⁻⁵. In the present communication, the work has been extended to the adducts of these halides with 10-methyleneanthrone in order to determine the effect of methylene group substituted at para position on the donor properties of anthrone.

EXPERIMENTAL

10-Methyleneanthrone was prepared and purified as described in the literature⁶. The procedures for the preparation and purification of various metal halides²⁻⁵ and their complexes³, elemental analysis of the adducts formed²⁻⁵, determination of molar conductance and molecular weight of nitrobenzene soluble compounds, infrared spectral studies and thermogravimetric analysis³ were essentially the same as reported earlier.

DISCUSSION

10-Methyleneanthrone reacts with various metal halides in non-aqueous solvents to yield a variety of complexes. It combines with chlorides and bromides of boron (III)

1. Paul, Ram Parkash and Sandhu, *Ind. J. Chem.*, 1965, 3, 277.
2. Paul, Ram Parkash and Sandhu, *Ind. J. Chem.* (in press).
3. Paul, Ram Parkash and Sandhu, *J. Inorg. Nucl. Chem.* (in press).
4. Paul, Ram Parkash and Sandhu, *Z. energ. Allgem. Chem.* (communicated).
5. Paul, Ram Parkash and Sandhu, *J. Inorg. Nucl. Chem.* (communicated).
6. Barnett and Matthews, *Ber.*, 1926, 59, 767.

and aluminium (III), chlorides of antimony (V) and bismuth in the molar ratio 1:1 and 1 with tin(IV), titanium(IV) and zirconium(IV) halides in the molar ratio 2:1 to form coloured solid addition compounds (Table I). Its compounds with iron(III) chloride, antimony (V) bromide and iodine(I) chloride are not very stable and could not be isolated without appreciable decomposition. The iodides of the above metals and halides of zinc, mercury (II) arsenic (III), antimony (III) and tellurium (IV) are comparatively weaker Lewis acids and do not react with methyleneanthrone either to form solid compounds or to change the colour of its solution. Any change in the solvent, molar concentration and reaction temperature does not affect the stoichiometry of these adducts.

TABLE I

(Complexes of methyleneanthrone with metal halides)

Complex	Colour	m.p.°C	Percentage composition					
			Calculated			Found		
			Ketone	M	X	Ketone	M	X
Methyleneanthrone-boron (III) chloride	Dark red	†	63.76	3.34	32.9	63.94	2.89	31.52
Methyleneanthrone-boron (III) bromide	Brown	†	45.15	2.37	52.48	45.64	2.02	52.13
Methyleneanthrone-aluminium (III) chloride	„	>220*	60.73	7.94	31.33	60.45	7.84	31.64
Methyleneanthrone-aluminium(III) bromide	„	>220*	43.61	5.70	50.69	43.40	6.74	51.29
2 Methyleneanthrone-tin (IV) chloride	„	>200 (dec.)	61.30	17.63	21.07	61.38	17.54	20.77
2-Methyleneanthrone-tin (IV) bromide	Light green	162.5	48.48	19.95	37.57	47.50	13.08	37.90
2-Methyleneanthrone-titanium (IV) chloride	Green	>250 (dec.)	68.50	7.95	23.55	—	8.50	23.33
2-Methyleneanthrone-titanium (IV) bromide	Dark green	>250 (dec.)	52.88	6.14	40.98	52.27	6.01	41.13
2 Methyleneanthrone-zirconium (IV) chloride	Red	>200	63.90	14.13	21.70	—	14.34	21.10
Methyleneanthrone-antimony (V) chloride	Green	174.5	48.82	24.09	35.08	40.56	24.14	35.23
Methyleneanthrone-bismuth (III) chloride	Green	182.3	39.54	40.06	20.40	—	39.87	20.57

†melting point could not be determined because the complex is very hygroscopic.

*melting point was determined in sealed capillary tubes.

Complexes were prepared in benzene medium except in case of zirconium (IV) and bismuth (III) chlorides where acetyl chloride was used as solvent.

The complexes formed are practically insoluble in benzene, chlorobenzene, toluene, cyclohexanone, chloroform, carbon tetrachloride and methylene chloride. They dissolve in basic solvents such as methanol, ethyl acetate, acetone, dioxane and nitromethane after decomposing into original components. Tin(IV) and antimony (V) halide complexes dissolve only in nitrobenzene to a limited extent. The determination of molar conductance and molecular weight (Table II) of these adducts in this solvent suggests their existence as n,n' -ionic and monomeric species in solution.

Boron (III) and aluminium (III) halide complexes cannot be easily handled since they are decomposed even by atmospheric moisture. All these complexes completely decompose on addition to water liberating methyleneanthrone quantitatively in the pure form except in case of its adducts with titanium (IV) and bismuth (III) chlorides and zirconium (IV) halides, where partially insoluble products of hydrolysis contaminate the ketone precipitate. Thus it serves as a simple method for the estimation of methyleneanthrone in the adducts of the former class.

TABLE II

Molar conductance and molecular weight determinations in nitrobenzene

Complex	Concentration (g. mole litre)	Molar cond. cm ² ohm ⁻¹ mole ⁻¹	Molecular weight	
			Calc.	Found
2-Methyleneanthrone tin- (IV) chloride.	1.50×10 ⁻³	2.40	672.7	630.8
2 Methyleneanthronetin (IV) bromide	1.976×10 ⁻³	3.32	850.7	790.5
Methyleneanthroncantimony (V) chloride.	3.94×10 ⁻³	2.58	505.5	478.9

TABLE III

Infrared spectra of methyleneanthrone and its complexes in 1500-1700 cm⁻¹ region

Complex	Carbonyl band (cm ⁻¹) I	Aromatic band (cm ⁻¹) II	Lowering (cm ⁻¹)	
			I	II
Methyleneanthrone	1660	1605	—	—
2 Methyleneanthrone-tin (IV) chloride.	1642	1602	18	3
2 Methyleneanthrone-tin (IV) bromide	1650	1602	10	3
2 Methyleneanthrone-titanium (IV) chloride	1660	1605	0	0
2 Methyleneanthrone-titanium (IV) bromide.	1660	1605	0	0
2 Methyleneanthrone-zirconium (IV) chloride	1645	1602	15	3
Methyleneanthrone-antimony (V) chloride	1640	1595	20	10
Methyleneanthrone-bismuth (III) chloride.	1652	1602	8	3

Infrared spectral studies.—The infrared spectra of methyleneanthrone and its complexes with metal halides were investigated in Nujol mull in 1700-1500 cm⁻¹ region in order to study the effect of coordination on carbonyl stretching frequency which is believed to be lowered on complex formation. With the exception of titanium (IV) halide complexes, a lowering of carbonyl stretching frequency has been observed in all cases (Table III) indicating the formation of metal-oxygen bond. These studies further reveal that the relative acceptor strengths of tin(IV) and zirconium (IV) halides with methyleneanthrone as a reference base, are in the order

tin (IV) chloride > zirconium (IV) chloride, and
chloride > bromide > iodide

which has already been proposed in an earlier communication².

Like anthrone⁷, benzanthrone⁸, 10-nitroanthrone⁹ and 10-benzalanthrone⁷, methylenanthrone also does not exhibit any significant shift in its carbonyl stretching frequency on coordination with titanium(IV) halides. Schwartz and Larson⁸ have also reported that the carbonyl stretching frequency of benzophenone remained unaltered on complex formation with titanium(IV) chloride. It seems rather difficult to attribute this constancy of carbonyl stretching frequency before and after coordination with titanium(IV) halide to the weak electrostatic forces comparable to hydrogen bonding forces because of fairly good thermal stability of some of these adducts. Probably it may be due to the synergic effect of two types of forces on the basis of which most of the data has been rationalised in an earlier communication⁸. Presumably the low energy d orbitals of titanium(IV) halides are available for an effective overlap with π molecular orbitals of the aromatic sextet. Thus the symmetry of d_{xz} and d_{yz} orbitals is quite suitable for an overlap with π molecular orbital of aromatic system if titanium(IV) halide molecule, flattened in the form of a square planar system, is sandwiched by planar ligand molecules. If this type of bonding were the only factor, the carbonyl stretching frequency should be expected to go up due to drain of electron density from carbonyl oxygen to fill the gap on aromatic system caused by the overlap of electrons of π molecular orbital of methylenanthrone with empty d_{xz} and d_{yz} orbitals of titanium. But in the solid state, d_{xy} orbital is in a position to steal some charge density from carbonyl oxygen of the other ligand molecule and the synergic effect of the two forces is such that the both balance each other without showing any significant shift in the carbonyl stretching frequency. However, this effect cannot be evenly balanced in all the aromatic ketones, probably this is the reason that the lowering of carbonyl stretching frequency is dependent upon the substituents close to the carbonyl group or on the aromatic nucleus. The formation of addition compounds between benzene and titanium(IV) chloride¹⁰, antimony(III) chloride¹⁰, tin(IV) and phosphorus(V) fluorides¹¹ further support the above mentioned mode of interaction between titanium(IV) halides and methylenanthrone.

Thermogravimetric Analysis: Thermogravimetric analysis of a few complexes has been carried out in order to understand their possible mode of decomposition. The analytical results, thus obtained, have been summarised in Table IV. Percentage weight loss per 5 minutes has been plotted against temperature to get thermal decomposition curves (Fig. 1) The 2:1 adducts of methylenanthrone with these metal halides have been found to decompose into thermally unstable 1:1 products. The titanium(IV) halide complexes exhibited another inflexion in the curve, which corresponds to the loss of half molecule of methyleno-anthrone for each molecule of the complex. Similar decomposition of titanium(IV) halide complexes of benzanthrone, anthrone and nitroanthrone has already been reported⁸. This characteristic mode of decomposition indicates that these complexes may exist as dimers at least in the solid state. It is further supported by their insolubility in most of the common solvents with which they do not react. The polymerisation of these adducts would increase the coordination number of titanium probably to eight. This coordination number is not altogether unlikely in view of the fact that Nyholm and co-

7. Ram Prakash,—Unpublished work.

8. Schwartz and Larson, *J. Less Common Metals*, 1963, 5, 365.

9. Cullinane, Chard and Leyshon, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1952, 4106.

10. Rankin, *Doklady Akad. Nauk. S.S.S.R.*, 1955, 100, 485.

11. Wolf, *J. Org. Nucl. Chem.*, 1956, 3, 285.

workers^{12,13} have already established that titanium attains a dodecahedral environment in titanium (IV) chloride-2-ortho phenylene bis-dimethyl arsine complex in the solid state.

TABLE IV

Thermogravimetric analysis of 2-methyleneanthrone-metal (IV) halide complexes

Complex	Initial decomposition temp. °C	Percent weight loss to get 1:1 product		
		Calc.	Found	
2 Methyleneanthrone-tin (IV) chloride.	52	30.65	29.98	at 214°
2 Methyleneanthrone-zirconium (IV) chloride.	57	31.94	30.77	at 312°
2 Methyleneanthrone-titanium (IV) chloride.	52	34.25	16.98	at 111°
			33.96	at 242°
2 Methyleneanthrone-titanium (IV) bromide.	44	26.43	19.32	at 111°
			26.40	at 224°

Relationship with other anthrones: The coordinating capacities of methyleneanthrone, benzanthrone, anthrone, nitroanthrone, benzanthrone and dibenzylanthrone¹⁻³ with various metal halides reveal that except for benzanthrone methyleneanthrone is the best electron donor. The lowering of carbonyl stretching frequencies of these anthrones on coordination with tin (IV) chloride³ lends further support to this order except in case

FIG. 1.

12. Clark, Lewis, Nyholm, Pauling and Robertson, *Nature*, 1961, 192, 222.

13. Clark, Lewis and Nyholm, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1962, 2460.

of anthrone where perturbation is slightly more than with methylene-anthrone. It may not be unlikely because the solid state interactions in different compounds may not be equal. This order is apparently reasonable because the presence of conjugated double bond of methylene group in methyleneanthrone may permit the movement of π electrons over the entire ring system, thereby, enhancing its donor capacity. However, benzanthrone should be essentially a better donor because π molecular orbital of the molecule in this case is common to the whole ring system. One of us (R.P.) is thankful to the Panjab University, Chandigarh for the award of research fellowship.

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